

GETTING ACQUAINTANCE AND THE CONCEPT OF GETTING ACQUAINTANCE

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Abstract

The article talks about information and examples related to the familiarization phase of communication behavior and the concepts of familiarization/introduction in Uzbek and English languages.

Key words

Communication, concept, addressee, addressee, communicator, Getting Acquaintance, Lexeme, acquaintance

When studying the concept within the framework of linguocultural studies, as in cognitive linguistics, the issue of the content of the concept comes to the fore, not the method of expressing knowledge in the minds of native speakers. Its linguistic and cultural specificity, in this sense, the linguocultural approach, in our opinion, is the most effective in comparing the concepts related to the awareness of speakers of different languages and cultures. This led to the selection of this particular approach as the basis for our study.

The concept is considered as a linguistic and cultural phenomenon at the same time. The meanings of words in different languages do not correspond to each other. They reflect and convey the way of life and way of thinking characteristic of a certain society. They are an invaluable key to understanding culture. This rule can be confirmed by words that objectify the concept of "Dating / dating" in Uzbek and English languages.

The explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language gives the following interpretation of the word "acquaintance": "Getting to know someone, communicating or getting close, getting to know each other and talking" or "Acquaintance is only the unity and daily life with someone relationship between people who know each other personally, who are connected in one way or another without additional relationships in life"

Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary, one of the explanatory dictionaries of the English language, defines the term "Getting Acquaintance" as follows:

- having personal knowledge of something : having seen or experienced something — + with

e.g. a lawyer who is well acquainted with the facts in this case

--I'm not acquainted with her books.

Another explanatory dictionary, "Macmillan English Dictionary", defines "Getting Acquaintance" as follows:

be acquainted with something

-- to know or be familiar with something, because you have studied it or have experienced it before:

e.g. Police said the thieves were obviously well acquainted with the alarm system at the department store.

Based on the definitions given above, the main definition of a night is to get to know, share, and establish a relationship with someone who is not familiar to you.

"Getting Acquaintance" is one of the basic concepts of any individual, collective, national, national relationship. concept, in the closest sense, in our opinion, is related to the concept of "own", the closest point of development is still the concept of "People".

According to the rules of etiquette, it takes place through an intermediary who is familiar to both parties, both in terms of marriage criteria and in the middle of dating. You can contact him to meet someone you want to meet.

After introducing them, you can tell how much he wants to connect with you by his response. If you feel that he is cold, it is better not to try to emphasize the continued connection.

An introduction gives you the right to talk to someone you just met. Usually, an intermediary is needed to make the introduction. A common acquaintance can be such an intermediary. Introduction or dating depends on the age, gender and place of introduction.

Where and when is it necessary to meet? First of all, depending on the circumstances, the person will be introduced or asked to be introduced. The main rules are expressed in the following words: "If I introduce you...", "If you allow me to introduce...", "Gulnora, get acquainted..."

The introducer introduces the names and surnames of both parties politely and clearly. The main rule here is: a young person is introduced to an older person, a man is introduced to a woman, an employee is introduced to a manager. The introducer says the name and surname of a young person first, then an adult, first a man, then a woman, first an employee, then the leader.

In general, greeting in Uzbek people shapes the attitude of your interlocutor towards you. According to Western custom, when meeting older women, one stands up and humbly shakes one's head in greeting. In our country, this applies not only to adults, but also to women in general. When introducing young people to an older person, they are usually addressed with a question;

M: *Ustoz, magistr Abdullayevni siz bilan tanishtirishga ruxsat bersangiz?, yoki Hurmatli rektor iqtidorli talaba Komilovni sizga tanishtirmoqchi edim?* Bu hollarda tanishtirilayotgan kishi ustoz hamda rektorning ismini aytmaydi.

They introduce a man to a woman. Depending on their age, young people are introduced to adults. Is a man introduced to a woman all the time, without exception? No, it doesn't happen all the time. It is up to the husband to introduce his wife to his friend: "My friend Sardar, meet her - this is my wife." Usually, the names of close relatives are mentioned first, and the names of acquaintances are mentioned later.

"Lexemes expressing the concept of "Tanishuv/Getting Acquaintance" in Uzbek and English languages are considered as separate concepts in foreign and local linguistics, "since the concepts are not closely related to any word, they are separated from each other. as it changes. Through words, they enter into relationships with various verbal forms.

The lexicographic description of the concept of "Tanishuv/Getting Acquaintance" "Acquainting with Uzbek and English languages, its structure and objectification in speech" is considered. Conceptually, the most important features are described.

In the Uzbek and English languages, the emotional and moral spheres are the main definitions of the concept of "Getting Acquaintance". Relationships between people connected in one way or another, processes of knowing each other are carried out through lexemes. They represent the concept of "Getting Acquaintance", which forms the basis of relations between people who are connected in one way or another and know each other.

The analysis of lexicographic sources in the Uzbek language made it possible to determine the lexical unit, language representatives of the concept of "acquaintance", including this definition of relations between people who are connected in one way or another, know each other and other people. Creates a lexical-semantic field of the same name, the center of which is the lexeme "Getting Acquaintance".

Lexical units representing the concept of "Dating" in the Uzbek language

Noun	tanish, do'st, o'rtoq, , yondosh, qiz do'st, uka, yigitlar, birodarlar, hamfikrlar. , sherik, hamkasb, hamroh, begona, muxlis, sinfdosh, birodar-askar, qo'shni, do'stlik, munosabatlar, sheriklik, xodim, qo'llab-quvvatlovchi, hamroh, chol, suhbatdosh, zamondosh, vatandoshlar, so'zlovchi, hamroh, hamkasb, xonadosh, ayol, ijarachi, sirdosh , dugona,
Adjective	yaxshi, eng yaxshi, yomon, yaqin, qari, eski, yangi haqiqiy, sodiq, samimiy, sadoqatli, , ko'p yillik, begona, tasodifiy, samimiy, katta, boshqacha, muntazam, ishonchli, jangovar, uzoq, uzoq muddatli, uzoq muddatli, kuchli, kuchli, katta, befarq qardoshlik, erkak , shaxsiy, kutilmagan, tasodifiy , qopqoqli (so'zlashuv), ehtiyotkor, qo'pol, ishonchsiz, vijdonli, jiddiy, diqqatli, beparvo, mas'uliyatsiz, beparvo, e'tiborsiz, takabbur, ijobiy, salbiy, insoniy, aniq, tushunarsiz, g'alati, ixtiyoriy, yoqimli , mehribon, foydasiz, qadsiz, axloqiy, zarur, hozirgi maftunkor, do'stona
Pronoun	meniki, uniki, uniki, bizniki, bizniki, ularniki, sizniki fikr, maslahat, yordam, qo'llab-quvvatlash, kelish, xat, tug'ilgan kun, portret, o'lim, oila, ota, ona, xotin, o'g'il, qiz, manzil, do'stning telefon raqami, o'rtoq, do'st, tanish
Verb	bog'lamoq, iborat bo'lmoq, yangilanmoq, tanishmoq, do'stlashmoq, tanishtirmoq, tavsiya etmoq, tanishmoq, til topishmoq, do'stlashmoq, uylanmoq. ajratish, etakchilik qilish, olib borish, ega bo'lish, qo'llab-quvvatlash, tushirish, xafa qilish, xiyonat qilish, saqlash, yo'qotish, qochish, bo'lish, o'rnatish, bog'lash, to'xtatish, davom ettirish, qo'llab-quvvatlash, ishonish, sevish, eslash, unutish, yordam berish
Phrases	<i>do'stga, o'rtoqga (ishonmoq), do'stga (xato qilish -),</i>

	<i>do'stga (biror narsa qilish uchun), do'stga (shafolat qilish, shafolat qilish, kafillik ~), do'st (aylan), do'st, o'rtoq (umid - g'azablanish, xafa qilish -), do'st haqida (esda tut, ayt - so'rash -. sog'inish, tashvish), do'st (sog'inish), do'st bilan o'rtoqlashish , do'st (uchrash. bahslashish -, janjallashish, yarashish - aloqani uzish - kimnidir tanishtirish), do'st (yashash - to'xtatish, qolish), bilan do'st (kelish, rozi bo'l. -. janjal). Do'st bilan (bo'lish, tashrif buyurish, tashrif buyurish)</i>
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Analyzing the semantics of lexemes in the lexical-semantic field "Getting acquainted with the application of the method of component analysis allowed us to determine the presence, closeness and uniqueness of the following general features, which seemed relevant for our study.

- attitude
- mutual assistance;
- joint participation in something, entertainment - the duration of the relationship,
- establishing relationships
- pleasantness, charm of relationships

The lexical representatives of the concept of "Tanish/tanishish" in the Uzbek language, determined as a result of the analysis of lexicographic sources, are studied in artistic and journalistic texts.

Analysis of explanatory dictionaries of the English language allows us to distinguish the main definition of the concept of "Getting Acquaintance" in the English-language picture of the world. Analysis of lexicographic resources allows to identify lexical units of language representatives of the concept of Dating/Dating, including someone you know and someone you don't know. The lexical representatives of the concept "Getting acquaintance in English" are listed in the following table: Lexical representatives of the concept of "dating".

noun	Acquaintance, friend, companion, comrade, mate, pal, partner, colleague, my dear, classmate, friendship, boyfriend, girlfriend, teammate, roommate, buddy, chum, felloow, fellowship, paricipant, collaborator, confederate, drinkin companion, ally
adjective	Best, bosom, close, dear, god,intimate, real, special, faithful, loyal, tru lifelong, old, female, male, fair-weather, person agreebale,amusingcharming, delightful, entertaining,pleaser wonderful, constant, traveling, drinking, unique, equal, activ chummy, buddy-buddy
verb	To acquaint (with), to introduce(to), to meet, to start, to renew, To resume, to be, to have, to keep, to develop, to establish, to form, t make, to start up, to strike up, to enjoy, to become, to remain, to sta to find , to win, to confide, to chum, to buddy
Pronoun	My, your, her, his, our, their
Phrasal verbs	To be acquaintanced(with), to be friends, to make friends, to find friend, to become acquainted, to familiarize oneself(with), to get o

	good terms, to be on a good team, to keep company with, to pa company, to fall into company
adverb	Friendly, comradely, chummy

The analysis of the semantics of the lexemes included in the lexical-semantic field of the concept of "Tanishuv/Getting acquainted" made it possible to determine that they have the following common features with the corresponding concept in the Uzbek and English languages:

- the closeness and uniqueness of the relationship,
- mutual assistance;
- joint participation in something, entertainment, - the duration of the relationship,
- building relationships,
- nice relationship,
- to complain

A comparison of the speakers of the concept of "acquaintance" on the materials of the Uzbek and English languages allows us to say that the main conceptual features in the description of relations between people for the Uzbek worldview are the closeness and specificity of relations, joint participation, fun, continuity of relationships, mutual support. In the description of relations between people in the English world, the main conceptual features are the closeness and specificity of relations, joint participation in something.

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